

Providing access to cost-efficient, replicable,
safe and flexible CCUS

Transforming Municipalities: The Handbook for Urban CCUS Strategies

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About ACCSESS

If CO₂ capture and storage (CCS) is to become a relevant, large-scale technology for cutting carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, several barriers need to be addressed, and its deployment must be accelerated.

ACCSESS works to address key challenges to the successful implementation of CCS across Europe: namely, challenges related to CO₂ capture, CCS chains, and societal acceptance. The project focuses on four industrial sectors with the potential to drastically reduce CO₂ emissions by implementing CCS: waste-to-energy, pulp and paper, cement, and biorefineries.

ACCSESS started in May 2021. Its consortium consists of 18 partners from eight different European countries.

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Abstract
<p>Urban areas account for over 70% of global carbon emissions, making their reduction critical in the fight against climate change. Although emission reduction efforts primarily focus on renewable energy, energy efficiency, and sustainable transportation, Carbon Capture, Utilisation, and Storage (CCUS) remains underutilised in municipalities - despite its potential to mitigate emissions from hard-to-abate industries. This Handbook provides an overview of the role of municipalities in facilitating CCUS adoption, as well as in highlighting challenges, opportunities, and best practices from municipalities and industry stakeholders.</p> <p>Through surveys, interviews, and workshops, key insights were gathered from municipal representatives, technical experts, and industrial actors involved in CCUS projects. The Handbook provides insights into the experience of front-runner municipalities that have already taken the first steps in leveraging the potential of CCUS for their Net Zero ambitions, an overview of cost calculations, and funding opportunities for CCUS projects.</p>

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

BECCS	Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage
C&DW	Construction and Demolition Waste
CAC	Cost of Avoided CO ₂
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CCU	Carbon Capture and Utilisation
CCUS	Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage
CDR	Carbon Dioxide Removal
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
CRC	Carbon Removal Certificate
DCM	Demolition Concrete Material
EU	European Union
EU-ETS	EU-Emission Trading System
FEED	Front-End Engineering Design
FEL	Front-End Loading
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
IEA	International Energy Agency
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
MRR	Monitoring and Reporting Regulation
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
UNCLOS	United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
WtE	Waste-to-Energy

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Carbon Capture, Utilisation, and Storage (CCUS) technologies are increasingly recognized as an important mitigation option for industries with hard-to-abate emissions, many of which are often located in close proximity to urban areas. The integration of CC(U)S into municipal environments is a topic of growing interest. Furthermore, urban environments are among the most significant contributors to global CO₂ emissions, particularly due to building operations, mobility, and industrial activity, highlighting the strong municipal role in addressing climate change mitigation. Urbanisation is considered a key driver of global CO₂ emissions, which are expected to continue rising as it accelerates, unless measures are taken.

A wide range of methods, such as nature-based solutions, transition to renewable energy, and sustainable transportation, are available to address emission reduction in urban contexts. However, CC(U)S technologies remain relatively underrecognized in this context. Despite their significant potential to reduce CO₂ emissions, especially from carbon-intensive industries located in proximity to urban areas - such as the cement, steel, and waste-to-energy (WtE) sectors - CC(U)S deployment has not yet reached its full potential. These industries are particularly difficult to decarbonise but are essential to economic growth and urban development, making CC(U)S an important, and yet underutilised, component of the climate solution portfolio.

As municipalities continue to grow and evolve, their role in shaping a joint future will become increasingly important, which will make it necessary for more municipalities to join the movement towards climate neutrality. The primary aim of this Handbook is to support an informed adoption of CC(U)S to achieve long-term climate goals and to move towards a climate-neutral future. It intends to shed light on the potential role of municipalities in this process and build on the experiences of the actors who have taken the first steps.

This Handbook was developed during the EU-funded Innovation Action Project ACCESS. It draws on two EU-wide municipal online surveys, ten interviews with stakeholders from CC(U)S projects and municipalities, as well as an online workshop showcasing best-practice examples of CC(U)S implementation conducted between May 2024 and February 2025. The interview participants included representatives from the Swiss WtE Plants Association, Celsio's Longship project in Oslo, the Port of Gothenburg, the Port of Rotterdam for the Porthos project, Öresundskraft's InnoZhero project in Helsingborg, Harbour Energy's CO₂nectNow project, Thyssenkrupp's Carbon2Chem project in Duisburg, and representatives from municipalities such as Trondheim, Zurich, and Gersthofen.

The insights from the data collection aim to support urban planners, sustainability managers, and leaders in navigating climate solutions, with a focus on CC(U)S technologies to reduce urban carbon footprints. It aims to deepen their understanding of the benefits and challenges of CCUS, helping them make informed decisions to achieve long-term climate goals. Furthermore, it seeks to connect industry stakeholders, municipal representatives, technical experts, and citizens.

Municipalities are shown to prioritize renewable energy adoption, energy efficiency, and climate adoption measures for emission reduction. Despite growing interest in climate mitigation strategies, results show that CC(U)S remains secondary priority for most municipalities. Only 18% of the survey respondents report that they are either actively involved in CC(U)S projects or exploring its potential. Additionally, 55% of municipal participants indicated they were unaware of CC(U)S technologies, while 44% reported having only a basic understanding. This highlights a general lack of familiarity with CC(U)S at the municipal level. The reasons for this relatively

low level of prioritisation, however, are likely shaped by a range of factors, such as divergent policy focuses or resource constraints. Nonetheless, we have identified three key areas that can contribute to the implementation of CC(U)S: (1) CO₂ capture at WtE plants, (2) public procurement of materials produced with CCS and of recycled concrete, and (3) the support of the CC(U)S logistics network. Special attention is given to capture at WtE plants, as they are commonly located in municipal areas and are often publicly owned, making them more directly manageable by local authorities.

The Handbook provides an overview of action fields where municipalities can take the lead in preparing and implementing of CC(U)S projects. Urban climate leaders can play a crucial role in integrating CC(U)S into citywide climate strategies, ensuring both emissions reduction and community resilience. As key agents of change, municipalities are invited to take the lead in planning and executing CC(U)S projects by initiating stakeholder cooperation and engagement, aligning regulatory frameworks, and fostering public trust. Public outreach efforts, including awareness campaigns and transparent communication, are essential to gaining community support and addressing concerns. Additionally, municipalities can provide financial incentives and support obtaining national and international funding, such as green bonds or grants, attracting investment and offsetting initial costs. Beyond local efforts, through active leadership, municipalities should actively create and join collaboration networks with other municipalities, research institutions, and private sector partners to share best practices, access technical expertise, and leverage funding opportunities. By fostering these partnerships, cities can accelerate innovation, scale up CC(U)S initiatives, and enhance their collective impact on global climate action. Through strategic leadership and collaboration, municipalities can champion sustainable development and pave the way for a more resilient urban future.

1 SETTING THE STAGE: CITIES AT THE FOREFRONT OF CLIMATE ACTION

The urgency of tackling global warming has never been more critical. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) has reported that human activities, in the form of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, have caused global warming, with an increase in global surface temperatures reaching more than 1.5 degrees Celsius in 2024 [1], above pre-industrial levels. Furthermore, global net anthropogenic GHG emissions have seen a significant increase of 54% since 1990, with the largest contributions stemming from CO₂ emissions related to fossil fuel combustion and industrial processes [2]. These alarming figures underscore the need for urgent, coordinated action to mitigate the effects of climate change.

1.1 Pathway to Net Zero: The Role of Municipalities

As the global population becomes increasingly urbanised, municipalities are emerging as critical players in the fight against climate change. Urbanisation trends are accelerating rapidly, with the World Bank [3] projecting a doubling of the global urban population by 2050, resulting in 70% of the world's population residing in cities. This growth presents both challenges and opportunities, as urban areas generate more than 80% of global gross domestic product [3] and are poised to become crucial drivers of sustainable innovation and change. Moreover, urban areas consume over 65% of the world's energy and account for more than 70% of global CO₂ emissions [4], which come mostly from industrial and transport systems [5].

Recognising both the challenges and opportunities posed by urbanisation, the European Union (EU) has set an ambitious goal to achieve climate neutrality by 2050. Central to this is the Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities, an initiative aimed at accelerating the green and digital transformation of urban areas by delivering 100 climate-neutral and smart cities by 2030. However, despite these encouraging developments, progress in Europe remains uneven. According to the International Energy Agency (IEA), among urban areas with populations exceeding 500,000, only 1 out of 5 [6] have proposed or committed to Net Zero targets and even fewer have implemented concrete policies to support their goals.

This gap between ambition and action highlights the urgent need for more municipalities to step up and adopt tangible measures to reduce emissions and foster sustainable urban development. As urban areas continue to grow and evolve, their role in shaping sustainable futures will become increasingly crucial, making it imperative for them to join the movement towards climate neutrality.

1.2 Handbook: Purpose and Audience

This Handbook has been developed as an integrated part of the EU-funded Innovation Action ACCESS, a technology-oriented initiative that also sought to emphasize the broader societal context surrounding CCUS technology. This Handbook draws on two EU-wide municipal online surveys, ten interviews with stakeholders from CCUS projects and municipalities, and an online-workshop showcasing best-practice examples of CCS implementation conducted between May 2024 and February 2025.

The interviews were conducted with key stakeholders involved in the implementation of CCUS projects for municipal carbon neutrality. The goal was to provide comprehensive answers to all relevant questions, addressing both those stakeholders that are already executing such projects and those planning to embark on similar initiatives. To ensure a balanced perspective, representatives

from municipal authorities and CCUS project teams were interviewed, offering insights from both sides of the collaboration. The input was gathered from representatives of the Swiss WtE Plants Association, Celsio for the Longship project in Oslo, Öresundskraft for the InnoZhero project with the city of Helsingborg, the Port of Gothenburg, the Port of Rotterdam for the Porthos project, Harbour Energy's CO2nnectNow project in Wilhelmshaven, Thyssenkrupp for the Carbon2Chem project in Duisburg, and the municipalities of Trondheim, Zurich, and Gersthofen.

The Handbook is divided into four different sections, starting with an exploration of municipalities' pivotal role in climate action, specifically focusing on how they can drive progress toward Net Zero emissions and what role CCUS can play. This is followed by a description of CCUS and its key implementation areas relevant to municipalities, and a description of several critical enablers for advancing CCUS projects in urban settings. The Handbook concludes with key takeaways for urban climate leaders and further resources. The Handbook aims to support urban planners, municipal sustainability managers, and leaders in navigating the complex urban landscape of climate solutions, with a particular focus on CCUS technologies. It intends to improve understanding of the challenges and benefits of CCUS and encourage municipalities to make informed decisions and consider the technology's potential to achieve their long-term climate goals. Moreover, it seeks to bridge the gap between industry stakeholders, municipal representatives, technical experts, and interested citizens.

2 CARBON CAPTURE, UTILISATION AND STORAGE (CCUS): A STRATEGIC INSTRUMENT IN URBAN CLIMATE MITIGATION PORTFOLIO

CCUS is a set of technologies that can enable drastic reductions of CO₂ emissions in energy-intensive industries, which are among the most challenging sectors to decarbonise. By capturing CO₂ emissions from industrial processes such as cement production, steelmaking, and chemical manufacturing, CCUS helps prevent these emissions from entering the atmosphere by permanently storing them. For this, the captured CO₂ can either be stored underground (the S in CCUS) or, to a lesser degree, be utilised in long-life products like cement or carbon composites (the U in CCUS) (see Figure 1). However, the environmental benefit of using captured CO₂ products is generally limited, particularly when compared to permanent storage, and is further influenced by whether the CO₂ originates from biogenic or fossil sources.

It is essential to distinguish the difference between CCUS and Direct Air Capture (DAC). While both technologies aim to reduce CO₂ emissions, CCUS primarily focuses on capturing and preventing emissions from being released into the atmosphere at the point of origin, such as in industrial processes or power generation. While the DAC method aims to capture CO₂ directly from ambient air.

CDR (Carbon Dioxide Removal) is a broader term encompassing various techniques for removing CO₂ from the atmosphere, one of which is DAC. When CCS technologies are applied to industries that utilise biogenic feedstock, this qualifies as CDR, as the biogenic component has previously “captured” CO₂ from the air through photosynthesis. An example of this is the process of bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS), which involves the capture and storage of CO₂ produced from the combustion of biomass for energy generation [7].

Figure 1. CCU vs CCUS. Source: Adapted citation [8] see bibliography.

2.1 Urban Imperative: Why CC(U)S Matters to Municipalities

Municipalities are actively pursuing ambitious climate goals through strategies such as improving energy efficiency, investing in renewable energy, urban greening, and encouraging sustainable transport. However, the lion's share of emissions and energy use is concentrated in cities, underscoring their central role in decarbonisation efforts [6]. As the emission profile of each municipality varies, the specific sources of emissions must be addressed for a comprehensive solution that leads to carbon neutrality.

Moreover, it is time for municipal representatives and citizens to become aware of the benefits and challenges of CCUS and to make an informed decision as to whether CCUS could be a beneficial element of their climate action strategies. In certain cases, CCUS helps address multiple urban challenges simultaneously, from waste management and energy supply to sustainable construction [9].

“We often say, we would have loved CCS to not be necessary and we could immediately go to the real sustainable energies and real green power. But it is highly necessary to decarbonize the industry now.”

~ Mark Driessen, Porthos Project

2.2 Understanding CC(U)S: Capturing Carbon Dioxide for a Climate-Neutral Future

CCUS refers to technologies specifically designed to reduce CO₂ emissions from large emission sources. The primary focus is on capturing emissions at their source before they enter the atmosphere [10]. The captured CO₂ is either permanently stored underground or reused (utilised) in various applications. However, the utilisation process can be energy-intensive and, in some cases, result in a significant carbon footprint.

CCS is generally a three-step process, including (1) a capture step, where CO₂ is separated from the flue gases of industrial processes, such as WtE plants, cement kilns, or paper mills, and then compressed or liquefied, (2) transport, where the captured and conditioned CO₂ is transported via pipelines, waterways, roads, or rails to a storage site, and (3) geological storage, where the CO₂ is injected into rock formations deep underground for permanent storage [11]. These formations - such as saline aquifers, oil and gas reservoirs or depleted oil fields - are naturally sealed by impermeable rock layers that trap gases. Liquefied CO₂ is compressed into a supercritical fluid (a state between a gas and a liquid) and transported, typically via pipeline, to the storage site where it is injected deep underground. Over time, the CO₂ reacts with minerals in the surrounding rock, gradually transforming into solid mineral compounds through a process known as mineral carbonation, which enhances the safety and permanence of long-term storage. [12].

In contrast, in CCU, the captured CO₂ is used in products such as building materials, adding value while contributing to emissions reduction (see info-box below).

CCU - Utilisation of Captured CO₂: With CCU, the captured CO₂ is used for industrial purposes. It can be repurposed for creating high-value products such as urea for fertilizers or integrated into concrete production. Captured CO₂ can also be used to cultivate algae, as they thrive on CO₂ for photosynthesis. CO₂ can also be used to produce hydrocarbons (e.g. methanol or fuels). In this case hydrogen is required as an additional feedstock, which can be very energy-consuming to produce. The utilisation of captured CO₂ remains an active area of research, with ongoing efforts to enhance efficiency, scalability, and the commercial viability of applications. **This option is not further described in the present report besides the public procurement of recycled concrete.** Further in this report the term CC(U)S will be used to describe both CCS (as a whole) and CCU (only for the public procurement of recycled concrete) that stores captured CO₂.

3 FROM CONCEPT TO REALITY: IMPLEMENTING CC(U)S IN URBAN ENVIRONMENTS

Where do municipalities stand now? Two surveys conducted in 2024¹ provide a comprehensive insight into the current state of municipal efforts towards Net Zero, with a particular focus on CC(U)S. These surveys show that municipalities predominantly prioritise renewable energy adoption, energy efficiency improvements, and climate adaptation as key strategies for emission reduction. Despite the growing interest in innovative solutions, CC(U)S remains a lower priority for most municipalities. Only 18% of the respondents say they already take a role (4%) or are interested in taking a role (14%) in the facilitation, promotion, and cooperation for CC(U)S development. Knowledge of CC(U)S also varies considerably among municipalities - 55% of municipal participants indicated they were unaware of CC(U)S technologies, while 44% reported having only a basic understanding. This highlights a general lack of familiarity with CC(U)S at the municipal level. The perceived benefits of CC(U)S, such as reducing the carbon footprint of energy-intensive industries and preventing climate change, are recognised by some. However, practical implementation is rare, though the reasons are likely shaped by a range of factors, such as policy focus or resource constraints.

3.1 Urban CC(U)S: Key Approaches

When considering areas in which CC(U)S can have the greatest impact on municipalities, three key approaches stand out: CCS at WtE plants to capture CO₂, public procurement of materials that are produced with CC(U)S technologies, such as cement and steel, public procurement of recycled concrete that contains captured CO₂, and support of the logistics network for CC(U)S.

“In the short term, CCS is just an additional cost, but in the long term, the cost of inaction would be much higher.”

~ René Estermann, Environmental and Health Protection of the City of Zurich

3.1.1 Waste-to-Energy plants

Municipal waste incinerators have been in operation since the 19th century, with the primary purpose of handling municipal waste while preventing landfills. Over the years, the technology associated with these incinerators has evolved from merely waste incineration to integrating systems that convert the heat generated into energy in terms of electricity and/or district heating and incorporating it into the existing energy grids. While this technology does address energy-related issues, a by-product of waste incineration is flue gas which contains chemical components, including nitrous oxide, sulfur, as well as CO₂.

The emissions from WtE plants typically contain a mixture of biogenic and fossil CO₂. Approximately 60% of CO₂ emissions in Europe are considered biogenic, which means that they are produced by the incineration of biodegradable waste, such as paper and organic waste, while the remaining 40% is fossil, originating from the incineration of fossil-based products, such as plastic [13]. By implementing CCS, the capture of biogenic CO₂ contributes to carbon removal [7], while capturing fossil CO₂ contributes to reducing fossil emissions (see Figure 2).

¹ The two online surveys were conducted by Fraunhofer IAO between May and September 2024. The surveys aimed to gain insights into the current state of municipal CCUS implementation. They were carried out within the scope of the ACCESS project.

Figure 2: Biogenic vs. fossil CO₂. Source: Adapted citation [14], see bibliography

When considering the implementation of CCS in WtE plants, two primary approaches can be adopted depending on the stage of the plant's development: integrating CO₂ capture into a new line or retrofitting existing facilities. Subsequent transport and storage will be required in both cases.

1. Integrating CCS in new waste treatment lines: The integration of CO₂ capture at a WtE plant can be done while constructing a new waste treatment line. This approach allows for better energy integration and more efficient planning and commissioning. The CO₂ capture system can be seamlessly incorporated from the outset, ensuring that the plant operates with reduced CO₂ emissions right from the start. This method optimises the overall design, ensuring that carbon capture is a central part of the plant's infrastructure.
2. Retrofitting existing WtE plants: The fundamental principle for retrofitting existing WtE plants with CO₂ capture is to add a system that captures CO₂ emissions from the flue gases in an operating plant. While amine scrubbing can be used for both newly built plants and retrofits, capture is typically limited to post-combustion at existing plants, with amine scrubbing being one possible method to separate CO₂ from the flue gas. This approach can be applied to existing plants where space and operational considerations allow it.

Figure 3. Simplified diagram of CO₂ capture system for WtE plants. Adapted from: Citation [15], see bibliography.

For early movers, the complete process of retrofitting a WtE plant with CO₂ capture can take between 86 and 127 months. A high-level Gantt with a lower implementation threshold is provided below (see Figure 4). Further information on WtE plant retrofitting and technical specifications can be found at the following link: [Retrofitting Amine CO₂ Capture to a WtE plant](#).

	Year 1				Year 2				Year 3				Year 4				Year 5				Year 6				Year 7				Year 8	
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1																									
Feasibility Study	█	█																												
Regulatory Compliance Assessment			█	█																										
Engineering and Design				█	█	█	█	█																						
Permitting and Approvals							█	█	█	█	█	█																		
Procurement									█	█	█	█																		
Implementation Phase													█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█						
Construction and Integration																														
Commissioning and Testing																														
Training and workflow Development																														

Figure 4: Gantt-Chart for the retrofit of a WtE plant with CO₂ capture. Source: Zhuravlova et al., Retrofitting amine CO₂ capture to a WtE plant. Own graph created based on interviews and NSP, 2024.

In both cases of integrating CO₂ capture into a new line or retrofitting existing facilities, the infrastructure for transporting large volumes of CO₂ is necessary. This requires a considerable amount of space, particularly when transporting CO₂ in bulk. Temporary storage at rail transport or shipping hubs is typically required, involving large storage tanks. Because CO₂ leakage from the tanks can be potentially hazardous and can lead to physical symptoms such as headaches, and in large quantities in enclosed spaces, even suffocation [16], the inclusion of safety distances is necessary, what leads to an increase in the overall space required.

It is important to ensure that the logistics infrastructure is reflected in the project timeline, as this constitutes a significant aspect of the overall plan. The permitting and approval process for such infrastructure might be lengthy and complex, given that it will require extensive space, often extending beyond the WtE plant's perimeter. Furthermore, negotiations with multiple landowners

are likely to be required, and opposition from local stakeholders is possible. Additionally, if a pipeline is chosen as the means of CO₂ transport, the lead time for construction is expected to be lengthy, adding further complexity to the project's execution.

Examples of cities that have incorporated or are incorporating CO₂ capture in their waste incineration plants include Oslo (Norway) and Hengelo and Duiven (Netherlands). In Hengelo, CO₂ capture technology has been integrated into Twence, the largest WtE producer in Overijssel. The new facility aims to capture 100,000 tonnes of CO₂ annually and aims to convert it into baking powder, or liquid CO₂ to improve the growth of greenhouse plants [17]. In Duiven, since 2019, AVR's WtE plant has fully implemented CO₂ capture, capturing an annual capacity of 100,000 tonnes [18]. Similar to Twence, the majority of captured CO₂ is utilised in greenhouse horticulture. The Oslo project is discussed in more detail in Section 3.2.

Thus, a WtE facility not only handles waste, but also has the potential to address the resulting CO₂ emissions by implementing technologies for capture and transport to storage.

3.1.2 Public procurement of construction materials produced with CCS and of concrete with recycled aggregates

Public procurement of construction materials produced with CCS technologies, such as low-carbon steel and cement, is a potential driver for achieving Net Zero emissions targets. The construction sector is a major consumer of emission-intensive materials, such as cement and steel, which are considered as hard-to-abate industries. These industries provide materials that are critical to infrastructure and urban development. By leveraging their purchasing power, governments and municipalities can stimulate demand for low-emission alternatives and create stable markets that support the widespread adoption of CCS. This signals long-term commitment to decarbonisation pathways. Embedding CCS-based materials in public projects helps lower the carbon footprint of infrastructure and aligns public investment with Net Zero goals, ensuring that climate ambition is matched by tangible, scalable action in the built environment.

The second option for reducing embodied emissions is the public procurement of concrete with recycled aggregates. The annual amount of construction and demolition waste (C&DW) in Europe amounts to approximately 374 million tonnes and the projected demand for concrete is estimated to increase by 12% by 2050 compared to 2014 levels [19] [20]. Within this type of waste, demolition concrete material (DCM) can be found, which is produced during the demolition of concrete buildings and structures.

DCM can be reused to create new construction material by utilising captured CO₂. This process is briefly explained in the image below. Mixing DCM with captured CO₂ and water produces solid limestone, which is, which can be used as foundation material for roads and buildings. This provides an alternative to the geological storage of captured CO₂. Currently, one tonne of demolition concrete can store around 10 kg of CO₂, with a potential of 25 kg/t [21].

Figure 5. CO₂ storage in waste concrete. Source: Modified after original graph by Luca Tschurtschenthaler, 2025.

Although demolition concrete that stores captured CO₂ costs more than conventional cement, its impact on the overall cost of a construction project is relatively limited. This is due to the fact that construction expenses are influenced by various factors, including labour, permits, and other logistical considerations, beyond material costs. For urban development, this allows for the *incorporation of emission-based criteria into procurement processes*. Municipalities can prioritise materials with lower embodied emissions, thereby promoting the use of more sustainable construction materials without significantly altering the overall cost structure of projects.

In the urban context, this impact can be achieved by modifying procurement processes so that recycled concrete is used at the municipal level, thus lowering the carbon footprint of the construction. The city of Zurich is a good example of how public procurement can be used to lower CO₂ emissions. In 2005, the city implemented a *requirement for the use of recycled aggregates in concrete* for public procurement, with a minimum proportion of 25% of aggregates being required, with newer buildings achieving rates of up to 50% [22]. The city also aims to reduce its Scope 3 emissions by 30% by 2035. In 2021, the city invested nearly 370 million euros in public buildings. This investment helps create a market for recycled concrete and obliges the private sector to use it. Currently, recycled concrete is used in all new buildings in Zurich, where feasible [23]. Zurich has gone even one step further. In 2013, the city mandated the use of CO₂-reduced cement [24]. These measures have saved approximately 17,000 m³ of virgin material, while also improving the lifetime energy consumption of concrete by nearly 5% [25]; additionally, the use of low-carbon cement reduces emissions by 25-30% compared with normal cement [23].

3.1.3 Logistics

The transportation and storage of captured CO₂ are crucial components for the effective deployment of CC(U)S technologies. Most captured CO₂ must be transported by different modes depending on the specific logistical requirements, to storage sites or facilities where it can be utilised (see Figure 6Figure 6), thereby creating new opportunities for infrastructure development.

Figure 66. Captured CO₂ means of transport for utilisation or storage. Adapted from: Citation [26], see bibliography.

Examples of multimodal transport for captured CO₂ are illustrated in Figure 7Figure 7. When selecting transport methods, key factors to consider include the availability of infrastructure, transportation costs, and the CO₂ emissions associated with the means of transport, as these will influence the overall carbon accounting.

Figure 77. CCS logistic chain example. Source: Citation [27]. See bibliography.

Municipalities play a critical role in the logistics network for CC(U)S, as they are one of the enablers of the necessary infrastructure development, such as storage terminals, transportation routes, and pipelines. By actively participating in planning and coordination, municipalities can help ensure the efficient and sustainable transport of CO₂ within urban areas. Furthermore, they are essential in addressing environmental considerations, such as minimizing the ecological impact of infrastructure development and safeguarding biodiversity during construction activities. The details on the costs associated with CC(U)S implementation can be found in the **Costs calculation section**.

Furthermore, municipalities have a responsibility to inform and engage citizens about the processes involved in CO₂ transportation and its local impacts, fostering public understanding and support for its role in meeting climate goals. This is especially important when captured CO₂ must be transported through populated areas, where concerns about safety and geological storage may arise, particularly in municipalities hosting industrial facilities with carbon capture systems.

The following regulations and laws need to be considered when looking at the transport of captured CO₂:

- EU-ETS Directive 2003/87.
- EU Directive 2023/959
- EU Directive 2009/31

CO₂ storage liability needs to be clearly defined, including regulations on how risks are shared and eventually transferred. In addition, compliance with cross-border CO₂ transport requirements must be ensured. More information about this key implementation and other CC(U)S technologies can be found in the following [link](#).

3.2 Bridging the Gap: Unlocking CC(U)S Potential in Cities

Several critical enablers for advancing CC(U)S projects in urban settings have been identified, supported by survey results, workshops, and interviews. Real-world examples from various European contexts are included, aiming to illustrate how municipalities successfully leveraged these factors to implement and advance their CC(U)S initiatives.

Research, Strategic Collaboration, and Innovation Opportunities: There is a strong emphasis on the need for ongoing research to improve CCS efficiency and reduce costs. This creates opportunities for municipalities to partner with academic institutions, other CCS projects, and industry leaders, or seek support from programmes and public funding. Collaborative efforts could lead to more effective, cost-efficient, and locally tailored CCS solutions, making implementation more feasible and attractive for municipalities. Additionally, collaborations that aim for targeted capacity-building initiatives, e.g., training workshops, pilot plant visits, more advanced CCS projects, or on-site support for infrastructure planning, can act as a catalyst for CCS implementation in municipalities. With the know-how to define system boundaries, conduct feasibility assessments, develop comprehensive plans, and determine potential investors for the necessary infrastructure (such as pipelines, injection points, or retrofitting existing plants), municipalities can position themselves as frontrunners in CCS implementation.

Trondheim has been actively considering CCS for nearly a decade, recognizing that its waste incineration plant is the largest single source of emissions in the city. In pursuit of their Net Zero goals (cutting GHG emissions by 80% by 2030), Trondheim applied for support from the Mission Cities program, highlighting its proactive stance in seeking external assistance for implementing CCS. A key focus of Trondheim's CCS efforts is its privately owned WtE plant. The plant receives and handles residual waste from 70 municipalities and industries from across Mid-Norway and supplies the city of Trondheim with thermal energy through 250 km of district heating-system. Successful implementation of CCS at the plant will **reduce annual CO₂ emissions by approx. 220,000 tonnes** (90-110,000 tonnes fossil and 110-130,000 tonnes biogenic CO₂ emissions).

Feasibility and Strategic Assessment, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Front-End Loading (FEL): Feasibility and strategic assessments help municipalities evaluate the viability of CCS initiatives within their specific urban contexts (see an example from the city of Zurich below). By conducting thorough analyses of infrastructure requirements, potential CO₂ capture volumes, economic impacts, and logistics, these assessments provide critical insights and support future decision-making processes. Additionally, they facilitate the identification of key stakeholders, potential partnerships, and funding opportunities, which are essential for successful project implementation. Feasibility assessments also enable municipalities to anticipate and address potential challenges, reducing risks and increasing the likelihood of project success. Furthermore, LCAs can play a crucial role in ensuring the sustainability and effectiveness of CC(U)S projects by providing a comprehensive evaluation of emissions throughout the entire supply chain. For example, Stockholm Exergi has utilised LCA to assess and minimize the environmental impact of its BECCS installation. They are targeting a 5% lifecycle emissions rate, which means that the supply chain and processing emissions would represent 5% of the total CO₂ captured and stored

by their specific project [28]. Based on the interview findings, CO₂nnectNow adheres to the FEL methodology: it systematically advances projects by addressing various aspects of the lifecycle, such as design, engineering, construction, operation, maintenance, and decommissioning. Through this structured approach, each phase is meticulously developed from identification to execution, with a focus on progressively defining elements like safety, environmental considerations, costs, and more. This process may involve leveraging existing technologies or innovating by conducting laboratory tests, pilot tests, and other validation methods to ensure that potential concerns are effectively identified and mitigated throughout the project's evolution. By supporting the industrial partners and combining feasibility assessments, LCA insights, and the FEL framework, municipalities can establish robust CCS strategies that maximise efficiency, sustainability, and long-term success.

As Sweden plans to be Net Zero by 2045, negative emissions are aimed at through CCS implementation at the **Norvik Port of Stockholm**. An overall proof of concept study was carried out with all participating stakeholders to clarify the prerequisites and conditions for establishing interim storage facilities at the port. Additionally, the Swedish Energy Agency granted funding for a more comprehensive feasibility study in May 2023. The study named NICE (Norvik Infrastructure CCS East Sweden) aimed to explore a CCS logistics node at Stockholm Norvik Port and examined risk analysis, potential business models and necessary permit considerations. The study brought together a consortium of industrial players, including Stockholm Exergi, Mälarenergi, Söderenergi, Vattenfall, Heidelberg Materials, Nordkalk, and Plagazi, to collaboratively assess the feasibility of creating a sustainable infrastructure for CO₂ capture, interim storage, and transportation in eastern Sweden. The study concluded that the port's existing infrastructure and strategic location are well-suited for this purpose. It estimated that the envisaged solution could manage a significant portion of Sweden's CO₂ transports, potentially **up to 9 million tonnes** annually, making it potentially the largest project of its kind in the country.

“It is extremely pleasing that Stockholm Norvik Port has the potential to be an important part of the solution to achieve national, regional, and the City of Stockholm's own climate goals.” [29]

~ Jens Holm, Chairman of the Board of Ports of Stockholm.

Regulatory Framework and Holistic Strategy Development: Municipalities can play a proactive role in shaping supportive CC(U)S policies and integrating CC(U)S into broader urban sustainability plans. By engaging with policymakers to advocate for clear governance structures, legally binding requirements, and tailored feasibility assessments, cities can create an enabling environment that attracts investment and accelerates CC(U)S adoption. Furthermore, including CC(U)S in broader climate action strategies and choosing the technology that aligns best with the goals of the municipality and existing infrastructure ensures that its value is recognised, helping to foster a comprehensive approach to sustainable urban development. This combined focus on policy and integration can streamline decision-making processes, providing a clear framework for CC(U)S implementation.

Zurich has set itself the goal of reducing GHG emissions by **95% by 2040**. To reach this target, Zurich plans to **capture and store approximately 436,000 tonnes of CO₂ annually**, with half coming from carbon capture and half from CDR technologies. Zurich has identified significant point emission sources suitable for potential CCS projects through feasibility studies, including the sludge incineration plant in Werdhölzli (22,000 tonnes of biogenic CO₂ emissions), the waste incineration plant in Hagenholz (40,000 tonnes and 50% biogenic emissions), and the biogas treatment plant in Werdhölzli (9,000 tonnes of biogenic emissions). This rapid identification and selection process was incorporated into Zurich's broader **Net Zero strategy**, underscoring the city's commitment to addressing significant emission sources under its direct control. Public support for these initiatives is evident: a recent public vote revealed that 75.5% of citizens approve of financing for CCS installations, making Zurich the first city globally to conduct a public vote on such a project.

Economic Incentives, Funding Mechanisms, and Business Models: Implementing robust financial incentives and funding mechanisms can significantly boost CC(U)S adoption. As new players such as chemical and infrastructure companies, engineering firms, and start-ups enter the CC(U)S market, they may be willing to cover the refurbishment and initial costs as part of their business strategy. To support them, governments can play a crucial role by offering tax credits, grants, or low-interest loans to support investments. Incentives should consider the interdependence of projects and favour entire systems and value chains to mitigate the financial risk for participating companies. Additionally, as stakeholders in public-private partnerships for local CC(U)S projects, municipalities can share those costs with other partners. Establishing carbon pricing mechanisms as a potential economic rationale can also make CC(U)S more economically attractive. Public procurement of low-emission products can drive demand for CC(U)S technologies by leveraging municipal purchasing power to prioritize products created using CC(U)S technologies, such as low-emissions cement, steel or recycled concrete with captured CO₂.

Oslo has set the ambitious goal of reducing GHG emissions by 95% by 2030, with CCS playing a pivotal role in achieving this target. The Klemetsrud WtE plant - the largest single emitter of GHGs in the city, responsible for 19% of Oslo's direct GHG emissions - is central to these efforts. CCS technology, tested at Klemetsrud as part of the Longship project, will enable the capture of up to 400,000 tonnes of CO₂ annually (50% biogenic CO₂ emissions). The total cost of the project is estimated at NOK 9.5 billion (~EUR 809 million), with funding shared among multiple stakeholders. The Norwegian state has committed NOK 2.5 billion (~EUR 213 million), while the Municipality of Oslo and Hafslund Celsio will contribute NOK 2.6 billion (~EUR 221 million) and NOK 4.3 billion (~EUR 366 million), respectively. In addition, there is state support for operation, transport, and storage over a ten-year period. Despite financial challenges caused by inflation, global instability, and a weakened Norwegian krone, Oslo remains committed to the CCS facility and continues to advocate for supportive regulatory frameworks, such as a reverse CO₂ tax, to enhance the economic viability of carbon capture projects.

Public Knowledge and Acceptance: There is a critical need for improved public knowledge and awareness of CC(U)S technologies and their benefits, as the survey results revealed a nuanced perception of CC(U)S technologies among municipal respondents within Europe who have limited knowledge about the subject. The perceived benefits centre around CC(U)S' potential environmental impact, with respondents recognizing its capacity to reduce the climate impact of energy-intensive industries, its role in preventing climate change, and its ability to make products more climate-friendly.

“People understand it. It makes sense. It's one of the projects to decarbonize the city.”

~ René Estermann, Environmental and Health Protection of the City of Zurich

While these perceived benefits highlight the potential of CC(U)S, several concerns persist that could hinder its adoption. Challenges involve the high investment needs and the associated cost-benefit ratio, indicating apprehension about the economic viability of CC(U)S projects. Additionally, worries are expressed about the risk of greenwashing and that CC(U)S might create lock-in effects for fossil energy. These perceived public concerns might lead to low public acceptance, which is not without consequences: the apprehension surrounding high costs and questionable cost-benefit ratios could deter investment and political support from CC(U)S projects. The fear of greenwashing might lead to public scepticisms and resistance, potentially undermining trust in CC(U)S initiatives. Moreover, the concern about fossil fuel lock-in effects could conflict with municipalities' long-term sustainability goals, making it challenging to get support for CC(U)S as part of a comprehensive climate strategy. However, municipalities can navigate these challenges by increasing both internal and public knowledge to foster acceptance.

Effective citizen engagement in CC(U)S projects to build public acceptance requires a combination of transparent communication, inclusive participation, and continuous dialogue. Municipalities can foster engagement through neighbourhood meetings, public consultations, and online forums that allow residents to voice their concerns and provide input. Engaging with local and regional media and utilising digital and print communication channels, such as geo-targeted ads, newsletters, and social media campaigns, helps to reach a broader audience and keep the community informed. In-person outreach, including the involvement of multipliers and agenda-setters that are trusted by the public, door-to-door campaigns, information stands at local events, and partnerships with schools, religious institutions, and community organisations, can further enhance awareness and trust.

“We believe that it is important that the municipality holds the voice, and we need to make sure that we have the citizens with us and not against us in mitigation strategies.”

~ Tove-Lill Karlsen, Climate and Communications Advisor at Trondheim Municipality

Communication and Stakeholder Engagement: To effectively advance CC(U)S adoption, improving public knowledge and acceptance is essential, but awareness alone is not enough. To translate understanding into support, municipalities must actively involve stakeholders through communication and inclusive dialogue. By establishing a comprehensive communication and stakeholder management plan, municipalities can ensure that CC(U)S plans are effectively translated to the public, enhancing knowledge and acceptance. To maximize impact, communication efforts should be guided by a holistic strategy that ensures all stakeholders follow a unified approach. This means aligning messaging, maintaining transparency, and coordinating outreach efforts to avoid inconsistencies or misinformation. Engaging external communication

specialists can help refine messaging and tailor communication methods to different audiences, ensuring accessibility and clarity. Communication and engagement activities can include formats such as citizen assemblies, information evenings, organised study visits for school classes, or booths at local events to get people's attention.

Effective stakeholder involvement goes beyond communication and focuses on collaboration and shared responsibility between municipalities, industries, private sector partners, and academic institutions. Open councils and forums provide opportunities for dialogue, allowing stakeholders to express concerns and shape project outcomes. These platforms also facilitate the timely dissemination of information, enabling stakeholders to make informed decisions and contribute to project development.

“[...] we involved all our stakeholders, both municipalities and politics at a very early stage. When we just had a plan, nothing was decided yet, we went to present the plan and get input from them and hear their worries and questions, if any.”

~ Mark Driessen, Porthos Project

Structured formats like expert groups, round tables, and cross-sectoral partnerships encourage the sharing of best practices and collective problem-solving. Industry consortia help streamline coordination, while academic partnerships enhance applied knowledge and operational expertise. By aligning goals and resources, stakeholders can foster innovation, overcome implementation challenges, and ensure the localised success of CC(U)S projects.

The Netherlands embraced CCS as a crucial component of its goal to be **climate neutral by 2050**. The **Porthos Project** focuses on capturing CO₂ from industrial sources in the Rotterdam port area, transporting it via pipelines, and storing it in depleted gas fields beneath the North Sea. It is a collaboration between three state-owned entities which jointly own Porthos. Porthos implemented a **comprehensive stakeholder engagement strategy** that prioritised **early and transparent communication**. They initiated stakeholder involvement at a **very early stage**, presenting plans to municipalities and other stakeholders like NGOs before any decisions were finalised, seeking input and taking concerns on board. This approach included "information evenings" during the permitting process, where documents were explained, processes outlined, and opportunities for questions and objections provided. The project invested heavily in stakeholder management, maintaining daily contacts with key stakeholders and identifying vital groups like NGOs or political entities.

Municipal engagement: Many municipalities report minimal or no engagement with CC(U)S, often citing reasons such as lack of interest, small size, or low regional priority within existing urban sustainability efforts. Moreover, because of the lack of clear funding pathways, municipalities are hesitant to commit resources to CC(U)S initiatives. Additionally, the complexity of CC(U)S may deter smaller municipalities, which lack the resources or expertise from actively engaging with CC(U)S technologies. Transforming limited municipal engagement into an enabler for CC(U)S initiatives involves developing tailored engagement programmes that highlight the relevance of CC(U)S to urban sustainability efforts, regardless of the municipality's

size. By establishing clear funding pathways through, e.g., grants, low-interest loans, or public-private partnerships, municipalities can be encouraged to invest in CC(U)S projects. Capacity-building efforts, such as technical training programmes and partnerships with academic institutions, can provide smaller municipalities with the necessary expertise to actively engage with CC(U)S. Additionally, creating collaborative municipal networks to share experiences and best practices can foster peer-to-peer learning and help overcome the perceived complexity of CC(U)S.

“The city has its own environmental managers, and they need to be on board as well. It's important to have a city's support, of course.”

~ Björn Fredriksson Möller, Öresundskraft Kraft & Värme AB

Legal and regulations: Local governments, developers, and other stakeholders must address several key legal considerations to ensure that projects are implemented safely, legally, and efficiently. Unfortunately, while CC(U)S has reached technical readiness for implementation, the legal and regulatory framework essential for its effective large-scale deployment and oversight still requires revision and updating.

The international and European regulatory frameworks are working to support CC(U)S technologies through global agreements and national laws. International agreements like the OSPAR Convention, the London Protocol, and the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) on marine law prove key to regulating waste disposal in the marine environment, thus addressing cross-border cooperation, especially regarding marine protection and seabed CO₂ storage. Further relevant international treaties focusing on climate change are the Paris Agreement, and the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) which requires parties to adopt policies and make commitments to reduce their GHG footprint [30].

On the European level, the primary regulatory focus lies on the EU ETS and the CO₂ Storage Directive [31], but further policies that shape the context of CCS activities are the 2020 Climate and Energy Packages, the European Green Deal, Climate Law, and the 2030 Climate Target Plan as they set the objectives and steps towards climate neutrality. Integrating the WtE sector across Europe into the EU ETS can be a driver for applying CC(U)S in this sector, while the CO₂ Storage Directive sets rules for CO₂ transport, third-party access, purity standards, and long-term liability. Generally, installations under the EU ETS must submit annual reports on their total emissions and surrender the corresponding number of allowances. CC(U)S activities can reduce the number of allowances required, as the obligation to surrender allowances does not apply to CO₂ that is “verified as captured and transported for permanent storage to a permitted facility”. The Monitoring and Reporting Regulation (MRR) specifies the points in the CC(U)S chain where an installation can deduct CO₂ from its emissions account: the capture installation, transport network, and storage site, as permitted by the CCS Directive. In line with the EU ETS Directive, which only includes pipelines as a transport mode, the MRR follows the CCS Directive's definition of “transport network,” which covers transport solely through pipeline networks. Consequently, if the liquified CO₂ is transported by truck, train, ship, or barge, the installation can only transfer liability and deduct the corresponding CO₂ amount once the CO₂ enters a pipeline network or storage facility [32].

Still, the burden of early movers in the CCS sector due to high capture, transportation and storage costs is significantly higher than the current emissions price under the EU ETS. This makes the CC(U)S deployment under the EU ETS economically unviable at present. This may result in delayed implementation. To overcome this, regulatory support to partly cover the burden of the investment costs could be sought at the national or EU level, e.g., through instance contributions to up-front costs, grants to cover engineering studies, Front-End Engineering Design (FEED), loan support (enabling preferential interest rates, access to debt capital, and loan guarantees), and tax credits. In this context, the [EU Innovation Fund](#), financed by revenues from the EU ETS, plays a crucial role. As one of the world's largest funding programmes for low-carbon technologies, it provides grants specifically aimed at de-risking and accelerating the commercial deployment of CC(U)S and other Net Zero innovations, with knowledge sharing as a key component. Another option could be seeking operational subsidies at the national or EU level to create predictable revenue streams. This could be achieved through, e.g., tax credits and/or contracts-for-difference [30].

“It's not the first option. It's not a silver bullet that can solve everything. It's one of the last measures that you should take.”

~ Björn Fredriksson Möller, Öresundskraft Kraft & Värme AB

In terms of national regulations and legal norms that potentially address CC(U)S projects, the national long-term climate strategy, including emission reduction goals and specific objectives towards Net Zero, as well as specific technological guidelines and limits, legally binding environmental considerations, and regulations concerning the national carbon market and financial opportunities for CC(U)S are worth considering. Furthermore, regarding permissions and land rights, CC(U)S projects may require specific zoning laws or changes to existing ones. Municipalities must ensure that the chosen sites are appropriately zoned for industrial activities and that land-use regulations are followed [32].

4 KEY TAKEAWAYS FOR URBAN CLIMATE LEADERS

This section provides a synthesis of the lessons learned from the pioneering municipalities and projects interviewed, highlighting successful practices and innovative approaches that can be adapted to various urban contexts. The following takeaways will provide actionable guidance for municipalities looking to integrate CC(U)S into their climate strategies, ensuring they not only meet their emissions reduction goals but also foster resilient and thriving communities in the process.

The role of a municipality in the planning and execution of a CC(U)S project is multifaceted and crucial to its successful integration into urban development (see Figure 8Figure 8). As a key agent of change, the municipality can adopt the role of a leader, carrying the torch of change and driving the conversation. The municipality's proactive leadership is critical in guiding the project through its early stages, laying the groundwork for effective implementation.

Figure 88. Role of municipalities in CCS project planning and implementation

One of the municipality's key roles can be to initiate the project by beginning the process of stakeholder mapping and engagement. This includes initiating and leading the stakeholder dialogue, involving all potentially relevant parties - from the potential pilot organisation to the operation phase. By facilitating open communication and collaboration, the municipality helps to ensure that the diverse perspectives of those affected by or involved in the project are considered. The municipality's leadership in this dialogue builds trust and fosters a sense of shared responsibility for the project's success, which is essential for long-term community support.

Another possible primary responsibility of a municipality in the planning phase is to align the regulatory and policy framework that supports the project. This includes ensuring that the project adheres to local zoning laws, building codes, and environmental regulations. By aligning the CC(U)S project with both national and regional policies, municipalities can help streamline the permitting process and ensure compliance with safety and environmental standards.

Furthermore, municipal support is pivotal in engaging with local communities throughout the project's lifecycle. Public awareness campaigns, town hall meetings, and transparent communication are essential to building community trust and addressing concerns about the potential risks and benefits of CC(U)S technology. By acting as a liaison between the project and

the public, municipalities can help foster a collaborative approach to environmental sustainability and mitigate opposition from local groups.

To build deeper public understanding and support, municipalities can implement citizen assemblies, where diverse groups of residents deliberate on CC(U)S-related decisions and provide recommendations. Annual climate surveys, including targeted questions about CC(U)S, can help gauge public perception and inform engagement strategies. Collaborations with universities and research institutions can also be valuable, as seen in Trondheim for instance, where students developed an educational board game on carbon capture. Engaging younger audiences through school programmes, interactive workshops, and partnerships with student-led knowledge platforms ensures long-term awareness and involvement.

Additionally, municipalities should work closely with local NGOs, industry partners, and other stakeholders to create an inclusive dialogue and address concerns. Providing financial compensation or incentives for citizen participation in decision-making processes can also encourage broader community involvement. By ensuring accessibility, maintaining open channels for feedback, and proactively addressing public concerns, municipalities can build lasting trust and support for CC(U)S initiatives, ultimately contributing to more sustainable urban development.

A checklist to ensure effective communication is provided below:

- Organisation of information sessions and workshops
- Regular consultation and engagement with stakeholders (e.g., residents, authorities)
- Use of online platforms for engagement
- Partnerships with educational institutions
- Maintain open channels with the community and ensure transparency throughout the process.
- Host public forums and discussion panels
- Implement feedback mechanisms
- Develop a community benefits programme, to show commitment to local development and sustainability

Financially, cities can play an important role in supporting CCS projects. They may offer financial incentives such as green bonds or grants to attract investment, helping to cushion the high initial costs of implementing CC(U)S technology. Additionally, municipalities can facilitate access to government funding programmes and assist in establishing partnerships with research institutions, private companies, and other levels of government to ensure that the project is financially viable and aligned with broader climate action goals.

By embracing this role and future directions, municipalities can position themselves at the forefront of the CCUS revolution, driving innovation, fostering sustainable development, and moving towards achieving their climate goals.

5 CC(U)S RESOURCES: TOOLS FOR URBAN IMPLEMENTATION

5.1 Cost Calculation

To calculate the total capital required for the implementation of a CC(U)S project, a bottom-up approach is recommended. Figure 9 outlines the steps and factors to consider when estimating the total capital required for first-of-a-kind movers. It is important to note that operation utility consumption may be 15% higher during the initial three years due to reduced capacity factors and increased maintenance and labour costs.

Figure 99. Bottom-up cost calculation method. Source: Citation [27], see bibliography.

To evaluate the economic performance, the Cost of Avoided CO₂ (CAC) can be used. CAC is defined as the ratio between the net present value of CC(U)S implementation costs, and the discounted amount of CO₂ emissions that will be avoided over the years. For pioneering chains, their estimated CAC ranges between 100-300 €/t CO₂. The amount of avoided CO₂ requires data on captured CO₂, direct and indirect emissions. As an example, for a cement kiln that captures approximately 775 kgCO₂/tClinker, with direct/indirect emissions of 125 kgCO₂/tClinker, the avoided CO₂ would be nearly 650 kgCO₂/tClinker. CAC can be assessed in two different ways, by doing a breakdown of chain elements, or by a breakdown of cost terms. Table 1 shows an example of how these breakdowns can look.

Table 1. Breakdown of Chain elements and costs

Chain elements	Cost Terms
Capture	Transport
Conditioning	CO ₂ emissions
CAPEX	Variable OPEX electricity
Fixed OPEX	Variable OPEX steam
Variable OPEX other	
CO ₂ emissions	

Geographic location is an additional factor influencing cost calculations, as it can affect energy and transport costs. For example, favourable locations, such as those near riversides that allow for barge transportation of the captured carbon, may incur lower transport costs. Furthermore, larger-scale implementation generally results in lower specific costs for capture and conditioning units, with a difference of 60 €/t CO₂ [27].

More information regarding the methodology for cost assessments, along with examples of first-of-a-kind movers can be found at the following [link](#).

5.2 Funding Opportunities

Various EU funding opportunities are available for CC(U)S projects.

The table below summarises other external funding opportunities. The columns represent different types of CC(U)S projects. Green cells indicate that the funding programme accepts projects of that type, yellow cells suggest potential acceptance, and red cells indicate that those projects will not be considered. Additionally, the table includes links to their respective websites.

Table 2. Summary of funding opportunities. Adapted from citation [33], see bibliography.

	CO ₂ capture	CO ₂ transport	CO ₂ storage	CO ₂ utilisation	Project development (including feasibility studies)	Specific Cities Theme
Innovation Fund	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red
CEF	Red	Green	Red	Red	Green	Red
Horizon Europe	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
ERDF	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Green	Red	Green
Cohesion Fund	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Green	Red	Green
EFSI	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Red

While these EU-level funding opportunities provide valuable support, it must be recognised that, as of 2025, the overall funding available for CO₂ capture and the broader CC(U)S chain remains insufficient to deploy CC(U)S at the scale needed to meet European and global climate targets. This funding gap highlights the importance of complementary national or sector-specific strategies to ensure early implementation and long-term feasibility.

For instance, the first steps of the implementation of CCS in Switzerland's WtE sector have been facilitated through a structured funding approach that ensures financial feasibility from the early planning stages. A key component of this strategy is the allocation of seed money, whereby all 29 publicly owned WtE plants contributed one million Swiss francs to a collective fund dedicated to research, feasibility studies, and initial planning efforts. This funding mechanism reduces financial uncertainty and enables systematic technological assessments before large-scale investment. The cost per plant is relatively low, translating to approximately 0.3 Swiss francs per tonne of waste processed, making it a cost-effective alternative to potential financial penalties under the European ETS.

While the seed funding is limited to pre-implementation research until 2030, a long-term financial strategy has been proposed to support the full deployment of CCS in the Swiss WtE plants. This would involve the introduction of an additional charge per tonne of waste delivered. This additional charge would be in the order of ten Swiss francs per tonne of waste. It would be designed as a flat fee, irrespective of the fossil carbon content of the waste, to avoid any disruption to waste streams and to simplify the process of collecting the fee. The revenue from this new fee

would be strictly earmarked to cover the investment and operating costs of carbon capture units built and operated at WtE plants. The level of the fee could be adapted to the deployment of carbon capture technology in Swiss WtE plants. It could be increased as more carbon capture units come on stream. Unlike in privatised markets where such financial coordination could be restricted by antitrust rules, this collective approach is legally feasible, as Swiss WtE plants are publicly owned. As the CDR market matures and negative emissions generate new revenues, thereby reducing the overall CCS costs, the fee could also be lowered.

This collective funding approach, where all Swiss WtE plants collect the same fee to fund one or more carbon capture units, would prevent any distortion of the waste market. Based on the interview findings, the Swiss perspective is that ideally, the operator of a WtE plant equipped with CO₂ capture would have no financial disadvantage compared to the other WtE plants not yet equipped. The operation of the carbon capture unit should not affect their balance sheet at all. Ultimately, the costs of CCS in WtE plants would be borne not by the WtE plant operators, but by the waste producers, in line with the polluter-pays principle at the heart of Swiss environmental law.

As an early adopter of CO₂ capture, the WtE sector demonstrates its viability. The gate fees are an essential part of the financial structure of WtE facilities. These are the charges that waste producers - such as municipalities, businesses, or waste collectors - pay to dispose of their waste at the facility. Gate fees are currently part of the established business model, covering the costs of waste processing and facility operation.

Adding capture to a WtE plant can provide new income sources and improve the environmental performance of WtE plants. Specifically, two major revenue streams can emerge from CCS: through avoidance of ETS costs and through sale of Carbon Removal Certificates (CRCs) for negative emissions. By capturing the biogenic portion of the CO₂ emissions, a WtE plant can generate negative emissions, which can be sold as CRCs. This market is emerging, with growing interest in both the voluntary and regulated carbon markets. The EU has recognised the need for such carbon removal solutions, and there is potential for these markets to expand. An EU-wide regulation for certification of carbon removals, carbon farming, and carbon storage in products entered into force in December 2024 [34].

Avoidance of ETS costs: WtE plants, particularly in countries like Sweden, Denmark, and Lithuania, are part of the EU's ETS, which requires companies to pay for the fossil CO₂ they emit. By capturing and storing the fossil part of CO₂ emissions, WtE plants can avoid these costs. This is a critical business model component, as it helps offset operational expenses and reduce overall emission-related costs. As carbon pricing continues to evolve, the cost of emitting fossil CO₂ is expected to rise. This is especially relevant for WtE plants, as the fossil part of the waste contributes to the emissions covered by the ETS. As of 2025, a comprehensive inclusion of waste incineration in EU ETS is still under discussion. Furthermore, methodologies for the certification of biogenic CO₂ captured from WtE plants are expected to be adopted by the European Commission towards the end of 2025.

By adopting CCS technology, WtE plants can avoid these rising costs, which will become a more significant factor in the long-term. This provides a financial incentive for municipalities to explore CCS integration into their waste management strategies. The funds generated from the sale of CRCs and saved by avoiding ETS costs can be reinvested into the WtE plant's operations, particularly the transport and storage of captured CO₂. This supports the financial sustainability of the facility while keeping costs manageable for waste producers and the community.

Based on the interview findings, in the future, there may be an opportunity for WtE plants with CCS, when some companies wish to pay a premium for climate-neutral waste treatment. This could apply to companies aiming to meet ambitious sustainability goals, where waste treatment with CCS could become a key part of their carbon-neutral strategy. While this is not yet a widespread practice, it is expected to grow over the coming decades as more businesses pursue comprehensive climate neutrality across Scopes 1, 2, and 3.

5.3 Further Readings

[IPCC \(2005\): Carbon Dioxide Capture and Storage](#)

[IEA \(2024\): Overview of Carbon Capture, Utilisation and Storage](#)

[European Commission \(2011\): Public Awareness and Acceptance of CO₂ Capture and Storage](#)

[ACCESS H2020-Project \(2024\): Neutral solution packages for CCUS implementation in smart, sustainable cities](#)

[Thyssenkrupp Carbon2Chem: Transforming Blast Furnace Gases into Valuable Chemicals for a Sustainable Future](#)

[Porthos: CO₂ reduction through storage under the North Sea](#)

[Trondheim: Test bed for climate neutrality](#)

[Oslo: This is what the CCS project means for Oslo's climate targets](#)

6 GLOSSARY

BIOGENIC EMISSIONS - carbon emissions that are part of the natural carbon cycle, which include the carbon released when burning wood. It is stored in and emitted by organic matter such as plants, animals, and soil. When plants, such as trees, absorb CO₂ during photosynthesis, they store carbon in their biomass. This carbon is released back into the atmosphere when the trees decay or are burned as wood fuel. Because this carbon is part of a relatively short-term cycle, it is considered carbon neutral.

CARBON DIOXIDE REMOVAL (CDR) - refers to deliberate technologies, practices, and approaches that remove CO₂ from the atmosphere. This also involves durably storing carbon after it has been extracted from the atmosphere, either in reservoirs such as vegetation, soils, geological formations, the ocean, or in manufactured products. CDR refers only to human activities that intentionally remove CO₂ and therefore does not include natural carbon removal (e.g., the growth of natural forests).

CARBON NEUTRALITY - a balance between emitting carbon and absorbing carbon from the atmosphere in carbon sinks.

CARBON PERMANENT STORAGE – when the storage duration of the captured carbon is +10,000, with very low to no practical risk of reversal. This type of storage includes geological storage, CO₂ in concrete, and mineralised CO₂ among others [35].

KG CO₂/T CLINKER - stands for kilograms of CO₂ per tonne of clinker. This metric indicates the amount of CO₂ emissions produced for every tonne of clinker manufactured. Clinker is a primary component in cement production, and the measure is used to assess the environmental impact or carbon footprint of the cement manufacturing process.

CLIMATE NEUTRALITY - when the emissions created throughout the production cycle of a specific product or service are offset entirely by climate protection projects. Climate neutral refers to the emission and mitigation of all GHGs – not just carbon. Much like carbon neutrality, climate neutrality can be achieved by emitting GHGs at an equal rate to their removal from the atmosphere.

DEMOLITION CONCRETE MATERIAL (DCM) - a waste material produced in large quantities during the demolition of old buildings and structures. The amount of waste generated during the demolition process is very large and creates several environmental problems. This waste is not biodegradable and is considered harmful due to the presence of cement within the mixture of DCM. It is normally dumped in landfills or illegal dumping sites resulting in the pollution of surrounding areas and consuming large amounts of space.

FLUE GASES - a mixture of gases produced by the burning of fuel or other materials in power stations and industrial plants and extracted via ducts.

FOSSIL EMISSIONS - originate from ancient organic matter that has been stored and transformed into coal, oil, or natural gas over millions of years. When these fuels are burned, they release carbon, adding new CO₂ to the atmosphere. This contributes significantly to the greenhouse effect.

FRONT-END ENGINEERING DESIGN (FEED) - an engineering design approach used to control project expenses and thoroughly plan a project before a fixed bid quote is submitted. It is conducted after the completion of a Conceptual Design or Feasibility Study.

GATE FEE - (or tipping fee) - the charge levied in the WtE sector on a given quantity of waste received at a waste processing facility.

LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT (LCA) - defined by ISO 14040 as the compilation and evaluation of the inputs, outputs, and the potential environmental impacts of a product system throughout its life cycle. LCA is a methodology used for assessing environmental impacts associated with all the stages of the production cycle of a commercial product, process, or service.

MINERAL CARBONATION - naturally occurring chemical reactions that bind atmospheric CO₂ with minerals. In nature, these processes typically occur at very slow rates, taking hundreds or even thousands of years.

NET ZERO TARGET – a situation where global GHG emissions from human activity are in balance with emissions reductions. At net zero, CO₂ emissions are still generated, but an equal amount of CO₂ is removed from the atmosphere as is released into it, resulting in zero increase in net emissions.

SUPERCRITICAL FLUID - a substance at a temperature and pressure above its critical point, where distinct liquid and gas phases do not exist. The substance is therefore in a state between gas and liquid.

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